

THE EFFECT OF THE ADDITION OF NON-ELECTROLYTES AND OF TEMPERATURE ON THE TIMES OF SETTING OF SOME TRANSPARENT INORGANIC GELS.

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The effects of the addition of non-electrolytes and temperature on the time of setting of some transparent inorganic gels prepared by the authors have been described in this paper. The heats of activation have been calculated by using Arrhenius' equation.

The addition of increasing quantities of non-electrolytes increases the time of setting of all gels, manganese arsenate gels being an exception. Increase in temperature decreases the time of setting of all gels, excepting those of sodium arsenate. The heat of activation is not found to be a characteristic property of a gel

Several gels of inorganic substances, which have been prepared in an opaque or translucent state, have been prepared by the authors (*cf. J. Univ. Bombay, 1938, 7, iii, 132*) in a transparent condition by suitably selecting the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures and adjusting their H-ion concentration. Ceric phosphate gels were prepared for the first time.

It is known that among other conditions, the time of setting of a gel depends upon the presence of the extra amounts of non-electrolytes and upon temperature. The effect of these factors on the time of setting of the gels, referred to above, has been studied in this investigation.

The effect of the addition of non-electrolytes on the time of setting of the gels has been studied by various workers. Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1929, 6, 991*) found that the addition of non-electrolytes decreases the time of setting of alkaline silicic acid gel-forming mixtures and increases that of the acidic ones. They further found that the effect of pyridine is peculiar in that it decreases the time of setting of both alkaline and acidic gel-forming mixtures. Hurd and Curver (*J. Phys. Chem., 1933, 7, 321*) found that ammonium hydroxide, methyl-, dimethyl-, and trimethylamines, pyridine and aniline decrease the time of setting of silicic acid gels while ethyl acetate, ethyl alcohol, acetaldehyde, and acetone increase it. Cane-sugar and glycerine have practically no effect on the time of setting. Parmar, Mehta and Prasad (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., 1936, A 3, 107*) found that the time of setting of thorium phosphate gels increases as increasing quantities of non-electrolytes are added to the gel-forming mixture. They also noticed the peculiar effect of pyridine in

presence of which no gels are obtained and the gelling substance separates out from the gel-forming mixture.

Fleming (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, **41**, 427) and Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, **22**, 516) found that the time of setting of silicic acid gel decreases as the temperature is increased. Fells and Firth (*ibid.*, 1925, **29**, 243), however, did not observe any distinct variation in the time of setting of the silicic acid gels on increasing the temperature from 0° to 45°. Bunce (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, **18**, 269) observed that a slight increase in temperature accelerates the gelation of mercuric oxide gels. Szegvari and Schalek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **32**, 318; *ibid.*, **33**, 326) observed that the time of setting of iron oxide gels decreases as the temperature is increased. Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 193) found that the time of setting of all the gels prepared by him decreases as the temperature is raised, excepting in the case of the gels of thorium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide and mercury sulphosalicylic acid, which take a longer time to set at higher temperature and above a certain temperature they do not set at all. Parmar, Mehta and Prasad (*loc. cit.*) found that the time of setting of thorium phosphate gels decreases as the temperature is increased. Hurd, Letteron and Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **35**, 604, 2194) studied the effect of temperature on the time of setting of silicic acid gels and found that the graphs obtained on plotting $\log t$ against $1/T$ are straight lines. They calculated the heat of activation during the formation of silicic acid gels by means of Arrhenius' equation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The non-electrolytes used were methyl, ethyl, and propyl alcohols, glycerine and pyridine.

Different amounts of the non-electrolytes were fixed with definite amounts of the solutions of either of the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures and the requisite amount of distilled water was added to make up the total volume of the gel-forming mixture to 10 c. c. The same solutions and the method of mixing were used in the preparation of each gel as described in the paper referred to above and the time of setting was determined in the same manner.

For the purpose of studying the effect of temperature on the setting of the gels, the solution of the constituents of the gel-forming mixtures were taken in two different test tubes and were kept for half an hour in the thermostat maintained at a constant temperature before mixing. The time of setting was then determined at that temperature.

Curves (not shown in the paper) were drawn for the time of setting against the concentration of either of the constituents for several mixtures at different temperatures and the times of setting for the same mixtures at different temperatures were read out from them. At least three such readings were obtained in the case of all gels. The logarithms of the time of setting were then plotted against the reciprocal of absolute temperatures and the slope of the straight lines multiplied by $2.303R$ gave the heat of activation. Owing to the narrow limits of the concentrations of the gel-forming mixture, the heat of activation could not be calculated for the gels of manganese arsenate, zinc arsenate and ceric phosphate.

In the following tables of results, Q represents c. c. of the non-electrolyte and X, c. c. of the constituent containing the anion in the gel-forming mixture. In the tables time of setting has been expressed in minutes unless otherwise stated.

(A) *Thorium arsenate gels.*

Thorium nitrate solution = 6%. Arsenic acid solution = 8.5%

TABLE I.

Effect of non-electrolytes.

Thorium nitrate = 5.0 c. c. Arsenic acid = 0.6 c. c.

Time of set for Q in minutes.

	0.00.	0.01.	0.02.	0.20.	0.50.	1.00.	1.20.	1.50.
Methyl alcohol	10	—	—	—	14	29	50	72
Ethyl alcohol	10	—	—	—	12	24	40	72
Propyl alcohol	10	—	—	—	12	18	28	—
Glycerine	10	—	—	14	25	180	—	—
Pyridine	10	—	30	12 hrs.	—	—	—	—

TABLE II.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 6.0 c. c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	0.80.	0.70.	0.66.	0.60.	0.56.	0.50.	0.40.
30°	1	3	—	8	11	24	12 hrs
35	4	8	10	28	60	—	—
40	10	30	60	—	—	—	—

TABLE III.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 8.0 c.c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	0.90.	0.80.	0.76.	0.70.	0.60	0.50.
30°	2	4	—	8	15	55
35	5	8	—	15	52	—
40	16	24	48	—	—	—

TABLE IV.

Heat of activation.

Thorium nitrate.	Arsenic acid.	Time of setting in mins. at			Slopes.	Heat of activation.
		30°.	35°.	40°.		
6.0 c.c.	0.76 c.c.	1.8	5.0	13.0	-7666 deg.	-35120 cal.
„	0.74	2.0	6.0	16.0	-8012	-36700
„	0.72	2.8	7.0	20.0	-8250	-37800
8.0 c.c.	0.90	2.0	5.0	16.0	-7750	-35510
„	0.84	3.0	7.0	20.0	-7786	-35670
„	0.80	4.0	9.0	24.0	-7714	-35340

(B) *Thorium phosphate gels.*

Thorium nitrate solution = 6 %. Phosphoric acid solution = 2 N.

TABLE V.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 5.0 c.c.

Thorium nitrate = 7.0 c.c.

Time of set for X in min.

Time of set for X in min.

Temp.	0.80.	0.7c.	0.60.	0.50.	1.00.	0.90.	0.80.	0.70	0.60.
30°	18	72	180	12 hr.	20	48	124	188	12 hr.
40	7	32	98	6 hr.	11	26	62	94	4 hr.
5		14	48	172 hr.	6	12	28	56	180'

TABLE VI.

Thorium nitrate.	Phosphoric acid.	<i>Heat of activation.</i>			Slopes.	Heat of activation.
		Time of setting in min. at 30°.	40°.	50°.		
5'0 c.c.	0'83 c.c.	13'0	5'0	2'0	3818 deg.	17490 cal.
"	0'80	18'0	7'0	3'0	3857	17670
"	0'79	21'0	10'0	4'0	3875	17750
7'0 c.c.	1'02	18'0	9'0	5'0	2615	11980
"	1'00	20'0	11'0	6'0	2643	12110
"	0'97	25'0	14'0	7'0	2666	12210
"	0'94	30'0	16'0	8'5	2643	12110

(C) *Thorium molybdate gels.*

Thorium nitrate solution = 6%. Potassium molybdate solution = 10%.
HCl solution = 2N,

TABLE VII.

Effect of non-electrolytes.

Thorium nitrate = 5'0 c.c. Potassium molybdate = 1'0 c.c. HCl = 1'4 c.c.

	Time of set for Q in minutes.					
	0'00.	0'50.	1'00.	1'50.	2'00.	2'60.
Methyl alcohol	2	3	6	12	—	—
Ethyl alcohol	2	4	7	10	—	—
Propyl alcohol	2	5	8	8	—	—
Glycerine	2	—	2	2		10

TABLE VIII.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 5'0 c.c. HCl = 1'4 c.c.					Thorium nitrate = 7'0 c.c. HCl = 1'4 c.c.				
Time of set for X in min.					Time of set for X in min.				
Temp.	0'80.	0'60.	0'40.	0'30.	1'00	0'50.	0'40.	0'30.	0'28.
30°	3	4	7	20	3	6	9	24	—
40	1	2	5	13	1	4	6	12	30
50	1	1	4	10	Instantaneous	2	4	9	18

TABLE IX.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 5'0 c.c. HCl = 2'0 c.c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	1'00.	0'80.	0'70.	0'50.	0'40.	0'30.	0'26.
30°	32	10	5	8	16	32	60
40	1	2	—	4	6	12	28
50	Inst.	Inst.	Inst.	1	2	5	18

TABLE X.

Effect of temperature.

Thorium nitrate = 5'0 c.c. Potassium molybdate = 1'0 c.c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	0'20.	0'60.	1'00.	1'40.	1'80.	2'00.
30°	2	6	4	2	8	32
40	2	4	2	1	1	1

TABLE XI.

Heat of activation

HCl = 1'4 c.c.

Thorium nitrate.	Potassium molybdate.	Time of setting in min. at			Slopes.	Heat of activation.
		30°.	40°.	50°.		
5'0 c.c.	0'40 c. c.	7'0	5'0	4'0	1100 deg.	5040 cal.
"	0'38	8'0	6'0	5'0	1085	4970
"	0'36	9'0	7'0	6'0	1083	4961
"	0'34	11'0	8'0	7'0	1125	5153
"	0'32	14'0	10'0	8'0	1077	4797
7'0 c. c.	0'40	9'0	6'0	4'0	1500	6871
"	0'38	10'0	7'0	5'0	1462	6699
"	0'36	14'0	9'0	7'0	1462	6699

(D) *Stannic phosphate gel.*Stannic chloride solution = 175 g./litre (SnO_2 content = 7.16%).

Phosphoric acid solution = 2N.

TABLE XII.

Effect of non-electrolytes.

Stannic chloride = 3.0 c.c. Phosphoric acid = 1.0 c.c.

Time of set for Q in minutes.

	0'00.	0'10.	1'00.	2'00.	3'00.	4'00.	5'00.
Methyl alcohol	4	—	7	18	36	92	—
Ethyl alcohol	4	—	7	12	21	44	90
Propyl alcohol	4	—	6	8	11	16	28
Glycerine	4	—	8	20	46	125	—
Pyridine	4	2	Ppt.	—	—	—	—

TABLE XIII.

Effect of temperature.

Stannic chloride = 3 c.c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	1'00.	0'70.	0'60.	0'50.	0'40.	0'30.
30°	4	14	26	60	185	12 hr.
35	3	8	15	26	70	4 „
40	2	5	10	18	36	2 „

TABLE XIV.

Effect of temperature.

Stannic chloride = 4.0 c.c.

Time of set for X in minutes.

Temp.	1'40.	1'00.	0'80.	0'60.	0'50.
30°	8	22	48	180	12 hr.
35	5	14	30	80	4 hr.
40	3	11	20	50	88

TABLE XV.
Heat of activation.

Stannic chloride.	Phosphoric acid.	Time of setting at			Slopes.	Heat of activation.
		30°.	35°.	40°.		
3.0 c.c.	0.80 c.c.	0.0	5.0	3.0	4286 deg.	19630 cal.
"	0.70	14.0	8.0	5.0	4280	19660
"	0.65	18.0	11.0	7.0	4250	19470
"	0.60	26.0	15.0	10.0	4250	19470
4.0 c.c.	1.40	8.0	3.0	3.0	3000	13740
"	1.20	12.0	8.0	5.0	3600	16490
"	1.05	18.0	12.0	8.0	3500	16040
"	1.00	22.0	14.0	10.0	3500	16040

(E) *Stannic Arsenate Gels.*

Stannic chloride solution = 175 g./litre (SnO_2 content = 7.16%).
Arsenic acid solution = 8.51%.

TABLE XVI.
Effect of non-electrolytes.

Stannic chloride = 3.0 c.c. Arsenic acid = 1.0 c.c.
Time of set for Q in minutes.

	0.00.	0.20.	1.00.	2.00.	3.00.	4.00.
Methyl alcohol	4	—	11	28	98	—
Ethyl alcohol	4	—	10	22	60	4 hr.
Propyl alcohol	4	—	8	16	36	112'
Glycerine	4	—	10	26	92	—
Pyridine	4	2	Ppt.	—	—	—

TABLE XVII.
Effect of temperature.

Temp	Stannic chloride = 3.0 c.c. Time of set for X in min.					Stannic chloride = 4.0 c.c. Time of set for X in min.				
	1.00.	0.70.	0.50.	0.40.	0.30	1.50.	1.20.	1.00.	0.80.	0.60.
30°	4	16	68	4 hr.	12 hr.	8	20	36	80	12 hr.
35	3	10	36	112	4 hr.	6	12	22	48	4 hr.
40	2	6	24	60	180	4	8	16	30	94

TABLE XVIII.
Heat of activation.

Stannic chloride.	Arsenic acid.	Time of setting at			Slopes.	Heat of activation.
		30°.	35°.	40°.		
3.0 c.c.	0.74 c.c.	13	8	5	4000 deg.	18330 cal.
"	0.70	16	10	6	4000	18330
"	0.63	23	15	10	4000	18330
"	0.60	32	18	12	4000	18330
4.0 c.c.	1.40	12	8	5	3733	17100
"	1.20	20	12	8	3733	17100
"	1.07	27	18	12	3617	16570
"	1.00	36	22	16	3500	16040

(F) <i>Manganese arsenate gels.</i>	(G) <i>Zinc arsenate gels.</i>	(H) <i>Ceric phosphate gels.</i>
Manganese chloride solution = 10%.	Zinc sulphate solution = 10%.	Cerium nitrate solution = 10%.
Potassium nitrate solution = 18%.	Potassium arsenate solution = 18%.	Potassium phosphate solution = 20%.

TABLE XIX.

Effect of non-electrolytes.

Manganese chloride = 4.0 c.c.	Zinc sulphate = 4.0 c.c.	Cerium nitrate = 5.0 c.c.
Potassium arsenate = 1.0 c.c.	Potassium arsenate = 0.3 c.c.	Potassium phosphate = 0.8 c.c.
Time of set for Q in min.	Time of set for Q in min.	Time of set for Q in min.
Ethyl alcohol 3 1 ½ Ppt.	— — —	44 42 56 72
Glycerine 3 1 1	5 2 3	44 52 60 90

TABLE XX.

Effect of temperature.

Manganese chloride = 4.0 c.c.	Zinc sulphate = 4.0 c.c.	Cerium nitrate = 5.0 c.c.
Time of set for X in min.	Time of set for X in min.	Time of set for X in min.
Temp. 1'30. 1'00. 0'80	0'60. 0'35. 0'300.	1'00. 0'80. 0'70.
25° 1 5 —	— — —	— — —
30 Ppt. 2 4	— 2 3	32 44 80
25 — — —	— — —	24 36 72
40 — — —	1 1	18 32 60
50 — Ppt. Ppt.	Inst. 2 —	— — —

DISCUSSION.

The above results show that the addition of increasing quantities of non-electrolytes increases the time of setting of gels in all cases excepting in the case of manganese arsenate gels in which the time of setting is decreased. These observations are in agreement with those of Prasad and Hattiangadi (*loc. cit.*) who also found that the time of setting of acidic gels of silicic acid is increased by the addition of non-electrolytes. It is difficult to explain the peculiar observation in the case of manganese arsenate gels on the existing ideas. The peculiar effect of pyridine is remarkable and is similar to that observed by Prasad and co-workers.

An increase in temperature decreases the time of setting of all gels except that of thorium arsenate gels which shows an increase. The decrease in the time of set can be explained on the basis of an increase in the agglomeration tendency and a decrease in the hydration tendency of the colloidal particles at higher temperature. The increase in the time of setting of thorium arsenate gel with rise in temperature was also observed by Prakash (*loc. cit.*) who explained it on the increased hydrolysis of thorium arsenate at high temperatures. This explanation may not hold good as at constant temperature an increase in the amount of arsenic acid in the gel-forming mixtures causes a decrease in the time of setting. A curious observation is that the peculiar behaviour noticed in thorium molybdate gel-forming mixtures containing 5.0 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution and 2.0 c.c. of HCl solution, to which increasing quantities of potassium molybdate solution are added, at 30° (*cf.* Prasad and Desai, *loc.cit.*) disappears when the temperature is raised.

The values of the slope given for different gels are not changed appreciably with an increase in the amount of the salt containing the anion of the gelling substance. The difference in the values of heat of activation with a change in quantity of the salt containing the cation of the gelling substance in the mixture is, however, quite appreciable. If these differences are neglected and an average value is taken, it is difficult to conclude that the heat of activation is a characteristic property of a gel, distinct from the other.